

USING INTERACTIVE FORMS AND METHODS IN TEACHING BIOPHYSICS AT MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES AND INSTITUTES

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Abstract. *The article examines the features of teaching the subject of biophysics in medical universities and institutes using interactive forms and methods of teaching as the most relevant at the current stage of teaching. Some forms are considered and teaching methods are provided for their practical implementation in the educational process.*

Keywords: *biophysics, teaching, interaction, innovative technologies.*

Introduction

The broadest concept, encompassing everything that surrounds us, is matter. Providing a simple logical definition of matter that would specify a broader concept is impossible. Therefore, instead of a definition, it is often said that matter is an objective reality, given to us through sensation. Matter does not exist without motion. Motion refers to all changes in processes occurring in the Universe. Conventionally, the various and varied forms of motion can be divided into four types: physical, chemical, biological, and social. This allows us to classify different sciences according to the type of motion they study. Physics studies the physical form of motion of matter. The various forms of motion of matter are interdependent and interconnected, which leads to the emergence of new sciences that lie at the intersection - biophysics, chemical physics, astrophysics, and others as well as the use of the achievements of one science to develop another. However, unfortunately, our teaching methods are often very inert and do not meet modern requirements. Modern biophysics teaching methods at medical universities and institutes offer a wide range of teaching concepts, methods, and technologies both traditional and innovative.

In today's society, active methods of teaching biophysics predominate. However, a more advanced method is interactive. It maximizes the development of communication skills, which is the goal of teaching biophysics. This article provides information about this method. The purpose of this article is to draw instructors' attention to more advanced and relevant methods of teaching biophysics and to familiarize them with the forms and techniques of this method to optimally achieve the communicative goal of teaching. The use of interactive forms and methods in teaching biophysics. Interactivity ("inter" means mutual, "act" means to act) means interacting, conversing, and conducting a dialogue with someone. Interactivity initiates more multifaceted student interaction, both with the instructor and with each other, unlike active methods.

The primary function of the teacher in interactive classes is to direct students' activities toward achieving the lesson's objectives. The teacher, of course, develops the lesson plan (usually consisting of interactive exercises and assignments through which students learn the material). Consequently, the main components of interactive lessons are the interactive exercises and assignments completed by students. A key distinguishing feature of interactive exercises and assignments is that, when completing them, students build on previously learned material, focusing as much as possible on learning new things. Interactive methods allow for a shift from monologue-

based learning to dialogue, where students can not only freely exchange judgments, their own opinions, and assessments of facts, but also have the right to argue with the teacher, defending their point of view and position. Interaction works when the teacher doesn't pronounce ready-made truths, but rather organizes students' search and discussion. "A bad teacher presents the truth, a good one teaches how to find it" (Disterweg).

Interactive learning involves students learning from each other, creating a friendly atmosphere of tolerance, security, mutual support, and understanding. This enables the development of cognitive activity through high levels of cooperation and collaboration in the acquisition of new knowledge. The essence of interactive learning is to ensure that the learning process fully engages all students, giving each participant the opportunity to understand and reflect on their knowledge and thoughts. Therefore, the individualization of each individual's knowledge through collaborative learning is crucial. Interaction offers the opportunity to share knowledge, ideas, and ways of working. Classroom activities also foster dialogue, leading to mutual understanding, collaboration, and the joint resolution of common, yet individually valuable, problems.

Interactive learning eliminates the dominance of one speaker or one opinion over another. As a result, students learn critical thinking, analyzing circumstances and solving complex problems, weighing alternative opinions, making informed decisions, debating, and communicating with others. To achieve this, lessons incorporate individual, paired, and group work, research projects, role-playing, access to various information sources, and creative work. Along with traditional work (work in small groups, pairs or threes, role-playing, or business games), interactive learning utilizes techniques such as rotating (shifting) trios, carousel learning, sentence completion, and fishbowl learning, among others.

In modern society, methodologists and teachers have developed many forms of group work for teaching biophysics. The most common of these are "outer circle", "small circle", "fishbowl", "brainstorming" and "debate" (the names may vary, but the essence is important). These forms are effective only if the lesson discusses a general problem about which students have initial ideas based on previous lessons and everyday life. Furthermore, the topics discussed should not be closed or too narrow. Spatial arrangement in the classroom.

"Circle of ideas" is a form of work aimed at resolving contentious issues. A list of ideas is compiled. All students are involved in the discussion. Groups must complete the same task, consisting of several questions (positions) that are asked in turn. In their responses, each group addresses only one aspect of the problem, and the teacher continues asking questions in a circle until all ideas are exhausted. This eliminates the possibility of a single group answering all the questions.

"Dialogue" - the goal is for the groups to find a consensus solution. The results of the work are presented in the form of a diagram or final text, which is then recorded in notebooks. The methodology involves critiquing the other group's position and identifying its strengths. The experts record their shared views, and at the end of the work, they provide a summary response to the task, which is then written down by everyone.

"Brainstorming" is a group method for generating ideas. When brainstorming, it is important to assume that there are no absurd ideas. On the contrary, it is essential to generate as many such ideas as possible. Neither the ideas nor the authors are judged.

"Brownian Motion" - students, like molecules, move chaotically around the room to gather information on a given topic.

“Take a Position” - a statement is made. Students approach a poster with the words “YES” or “NO”. It is preferable that they explain their position.

“Discussion” - educational group discussions are held on a chosen problem in small groups (12 to 14 students). An educational discussion differs from other discussions in that the problem being discussed is new only to the group participating in the discussion; that is, an already known solution to the problem must be discovered through the educational process. The search process should lead to objectively known knowledge, but new from the students' perspective.

“Debate” is an example (excerpt) of a lesson using debate as a form of work. Objective: to develop skills in collaborative communication, critical thinking, group interaction, and tolerance of opposition.

Lesson stages: 1. Warm-up. It is assumed that this is not the first lesson in the series on the topic “Hemodynamics” meaning that the students are already familiar with it. The teacher poses the question, “What is Hemodynamics?” to the students, and they share their opinions. 2. Divide the students into working groups. Groups are created based on the student's previously expressed opinion. 3. Introduce students to debate techniques (it is especially important to clearly explain the rules if this form of work is being used for the first time). The teacher should explain the goals and objectives of each group. A timekeeper (a person who will monitor the rules) is selected. The timekeeper indicates when 3 minutes, 2 minutes, 1 minute, and 30 seconds remain. A panel of judges is appointed. 4. The time limit for each statement is set (e.g., 5 minutes), and the discussion begins, choosing debate tactics (if the group is prepared, mini-debates can begin after 10-15 minutes; in this case, each speaker's speaking time should be reduced to 2-3 minutes). Debate preparation can generally be completed over a two-week period.

Group work format: “Rotating trios” - the composition of the groups (trios) changes during the lesson. “Decision tree” - the class is divided into several groups with an equal number of students. Each group discusses the issue and makes notes on the board (a piece of paper or a chalkboard). The groups then switch places and add their thoughts to their neighbors' boards. “Common project” - groups are given various assignments that address the issue from different perspectives. After completing the work, reports are prepared and notes are made on the board. These notes are compiled into a common project, which is reviewed and supplemented by a group of experts. “Thought Synthesis” is a copy of the previous method, with the difference that students write down all their notes on sheets of paper, which they then pass to the next group. The sheets are then used to highlight ideas the group disagrees with. The experts process the sheets and produce a general report, which is then discussed by the entire class of students. “Information Search” is a method used to enliven dry and uninteresting material. It involves a team search for information that complements what's already available (a lecture or homework). Students then answer questions. The answers to the questions should be found in textbooks or handouts. A limited amount of time is given to analyze the information and find answers to the questions.

Conclusion: Thus, a large number of interactive learning methods and forms have been developed to date. However, every progressive teacher can develop their own approaches to working with students. Most of the interactive methods listed above relate to corporate learning technologies, where students collaborate to complete assignments, master the material, and develop communication skills during discussions and arguments. A huge advantage of this type of learning activity is that all students in the class are involved in the shared work. The challenge lies in organizing student activity and engaging them in this type of work as a regular part of the process. The methods mentioned in this article can serve as a basis for developing new forms. The

interactive creativity of both teacher and student is limitless and this is the main advantage of interactive learning.

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